

EDUCATIONAL GAMES AND THEIR ORGANIZATION IN SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, there is a word about children with disabilities in speech, hearing, intellectual ability, physical and mental development, conducting useful games to correct their disabilities in special kindergartens and special schools, and to eliminate their disabilities even if they are small. goes

Key words: speech, speech therapy games, national games, games that develop fine motor skills, games aimed at correct pronunciation of sounds, games aimed at developing breathing, games aimed at developing voice, games aimed at developing hearing.

Special games are organized for the development of speech, hearing, physical and mental condition of children of preschool and school age. Based on these games, children's cognitive processes, large and small motor skills develop. Through these games, children can acquire their future professions. Children's thinking ability develops with games. Every game has its importance in human life. Children develop their abilities, information they receive from the external environment, and their speech through the game. Young children are very attentive. They listen carefully to every word of the adults and use the words they hear in the game. Adults should try to use more new words when communicating with children. learn new words and try to use these new words during the game. Parents should pay attention to every word when communicating with their children. If a mother or father mispronounces words while speaking to a child, or intentionally mispronounces words to flatter their child, the child is mispronouncing the words as if they heard them from the parent even while speaking. may develop.

Logopedic play sessions with children are as follows:

1. Exercises related to the development of breathing
2. Games that develop voice
3. Games that stimulate auditory attention
4. Games that develop the speech apparatus
5. Factors that eliminate deficiencies in the pronunciation of sounds
6. Games that eliminate stuttering
7. Games for the development of small hand motor skills.

Based on these games, it will be possible to eliminate the shortcomings in children's speech. By correcting each defect with games, it is possible to develop children's cognitive processes, i.e., attention, memory, perception, thinking, and imagination. will be well developed. Children with well-developed perception perceive the shape and size of what they see well. Children remember things and events in 3 different ways: seeing, hearing and holding (touching). Games are very important for their development.

Games are divided into two types:

1. Creative games
2. Regular games

In creative games, there are no specific laws and rules, the events of the game are invented by the children themselves. By playing creative games, children develop the skills to choose their future professions. Several children play such games together. For example: games like "aunt-aunt", "doctor-doctor", "cooking". Children themselves determine the course of events in these games. Children who play "Doctor-Doctor" may become doctors in the future. Children who play cooking games can develop the desire to become a great chef. In creative games, children show what conditions prevail in their family. For example: girls shape their mother's character, and boys shape their father's character. They repeat the words they heard from their parents during the game. In the process of such a game, children develop acting and acting skills.

In rule-based games, children play based on certain established rules. Games with rules include: didactic games, action games, musical games, etc. In order to organize games, pedagogues need to take into account children's interests and their shortcomings. The famous pedagogue and doctor N.A. Arkin calls the game a mental vitamin. He didn't name it for nothing. Through play, the child develops in all aspects. Through didactic games, children's thinking, memory, thinking, attention, imagination, and vocabulary improve.

Games can be divided into several groups depending on their idea and content:

1. Games depicting domestic life ("family", "hospital", "kindergarten").
2. Games depicting the labor process ("construction", "farmers' work", "construction of houses and factories", etc.).
3. Games depicting social events and traditions (holidays, demonstrations, travel, waiting for guests, etc.)

Each game is played based on life events. When children play each game, they play the role of the character in that game and reflect life events in these roles.

National games develop children's respect for national values and rules such as ethics and aesthetics. Through national games, we learn the feelings of patriotism and national sayings that have come down to us from our ancestors.

National games are also divided into groups:

1. Seasonal children's national games: national games played in the spring, summer, autumn, and winter seasons.
2. Ritual games adapted for children: games played during rituals, customs, ceremonies, traditional holidays.
3. National games related to work: "planting crops", "plowing the land", "strawberry picking", "milking a cow", "watering a horse" and others.
4. Family-household children's national games: "Guest-guest", "Bride drop-off", "Mother-child", "Doll game", "Alla-alla", "Cradle play" and others.
5. National games for physically active children: "Quvlashmachok", "goose-goose", "rabbit-rabbit", "ball", "white bone", "zuv-zuv", "white poplar- blue poplar", "donkey rode", "long-eared" and others.
6. Games that increase logical thinking: quick sayings, riddles, counting, questions and answers, guesswork, etc.
7. Children's games related to animals and natural phenomena.
8. Ermak children's national games

9. Music games.

All of the above games instill in children such services as patriotism, community, friendship, harmony, hard work, wisdom, kindness, courage, bravery, hospitality, dexterity and achievement. Children who embody these qualities will grow up to become mature people who will gladly serve the country in the future.

For the full development of children's speech, it is necessary for the speech center in the cerebral cortex to be well developed. Along with the good development of this center, it is necessary that their senses: hearing, sight, full knowledge and skin feel are sufficiently developed. Proper breathing, normal development of hearing and voice play an important role in the all-round development of a child.

1. Children can play the following games to improve breathing.

For example, a speech therapist can work with children using the "Butterflies are flying" method to help them breathe properly. In this case, the speech therapist should place paper butterflies in front of the children and ask them whose butterfly will fly the farthest. Then the children blow on the butterflies to make them fly. This method can be repeated several times.

In the game "In the chicken farm", the speech therapist shows the children several toys and imitates their voices, and after taking the toys from the table, he asks the children that we have now gone to the chicken farm, what sounds do the birds there make? he says and takes a toy and shows it to the children and tells them what the sound of this bird is. Children imitate the sound of the pedagogue by looking at the toy in his hand. This game helps to improve the child's memory, hearing and breathing.

"Football" game - in this game, the pedagogue tells the children that we will play football with you, but we will blow with our mouths, not with our feet. He makes a gate out of a ruler on the table for the children, and a ball out of cotton. Children try to score goals with their mouths. A speech therapist monitors children's breathing.

2. Games for voice development.

The game "The wind is blowing" - in this game, the speech therapist leads the students in a semicircle and tells them to imagine that we went to the forest, where a gentle wind is blowing, and the flowers and grass are shaking, and asks the children what the sound of the wind is. 'rides. First, the speech therapist himself pronounces the sound to the children, and the children pronounce the sound after the pedagogue. The speech therapist pronounces the sound by raising it and lowering it, and the children repeat the same.

"Cat and mouse" game in which children stand in a circle and a child in the role of a cat stands in the middle. A boy in the role of a mouse stands outside the circle. The child in the role of the cat speaks loudly, and the child in the role of the mouse speaks softly. It is possible to develop the tones of the child's voice, that is, the high and low pitch of the voice.

3. Games that develop auditory attention.

The game "Sun and rain" in which the speech therapist tells the children that we went for a walk, the sun is rising, but there is a chance of rain drops. If the pedagogue begins to click the circle slowly, it means that it has started to rain. At this time, the children will have to run away to their homes. Such games develop children's hearing skills well.

4. Games aimed at developing phonemic perception and speech hearing.

The game "Red and white" - each child is given red and white papers. The teacher says a sound, and if the children hear this sound between the words, they must pick up the red

paper. if they don't hear the sound that the pedagogue said between the words, they raise the white paper. Through this game, their hearing and phonemic perception develop well.

5. Exercises to increase the mobility of the speech apparatus.

In the game "Sweet jam", the speech therapist shows the children a picture of a girl licking jam, and while licking the jam, the girl touches her upper and lower lips with jam, and now she wants to clean it with her tongue and asks how she does it. Children demonstrate the exercise by rolling their tongue around the mouth. The purpose of this game is to develop the articulatory apparatus. In order for the child to be healthy in all respects, parents should pay attention to their child. If a mother communicates more with her child, the development of her speech will accelerate, and the child's vocabulary will increase.

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